

Water structure in the first layers on TiO₂: a key factor for boosting solar-driven water-splitting performances

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Photocatalytic water splitting is a promising method to produce green hydrogen (H₂) using direct solar energy.¹ However, several technological improvements are still required to enhance the performance of this process and make it competitive on a large scale. As it is known, the efficiency of the overall water-splitting process depends on three main factors:²⁻⁴ i) the light-harvesting ability of a semiconductor, ii) the charge separation/transfer efficiency, and iii) the surface reactions for the H₂ and O₂ generation. Until now, several efforts have been devoted to developing stable and cost-effective photocatalysts with suitable physical-chemical properties and high activity for H₂ generation. Among them, modifications of the semiconductor bandgap, the identification of the specific crystal facets involved, and the morphology or formation of heterojunctions are traditionally considered key factors responsible for enhanced H₂ generation rates.⁵⁻⁷ Conversely, the role played by the first molecular layers of water at the interface with a semiconductor (*i.e.*, the Stern layer within the Helmholtz diffuse layer) is generally not considered a relevant variable in the overall H₂ production process.

Nonetheless, knowledge of the hydrogen (H-) bond network structure near (and beyond) a photocatalyst surface represents an emerging hot topic in photocatalysis. Recent studies reveal that peculiar topologies of the H-bond network may promote interfacial charge transfer, providing valuable insights for engineering more efficient future photocatalytic materials.⁸⁻¹¹ Moreover, photoinduced water splitting is enhanced by adding H₂O molecules beyond the initial monolayer at the aqueous/catalyst interface.¹² Although all this evidence indicates that the local aqueous environment might be designed in such a way to maximise the performances of the overall process, very few investigations aimed explicitly at ascertaining the role played by water and its H-bond network in photocatalytic H₂ production.¹²⁻¹⁴

Considering that the structure of interfacial water differs from that of the bulk as the predominantly tetrahedral H-bond network is sizably altered by a solid surface,¹⁵⁻¹⁷ further investigations are mandatory for a clear comprehension of the role of the H-bond network in photocatalysis and particularly in determining water splitting rate. It is worth emphasising that, albeit local, the water environment's structural modifications near a solid surface may influence the electron transfer reactions and electrocatalytic activity.¹⁸ According to the Marcus theory, the electron transfer rate, especially in outer-shell electron transfer mechanisms, is determined from the solvent reorganisation and thus strongly depends on the solvent's first-layer (molecular) structure.¹⁹⁻²¹

Upon modification of the properties of the surface of a semiconductor (e.g., by doping), changes may be expected in the water first layers of the liquid-solid interface, influencing the outer-sphere electron transfer reactions.^{22,23}

In this paper, we investigate the molecular arrangement of water at the semiconductor interface and ascertain to which extent the local water's structure at the liquid-solid interface differs from that found in the electric double layer (EDL) and the bulk of water. Furthermore, we assess its impact on the kinetics of the photocatalytic water-splitting phenomenon. To answer this challenging question, we synthesised two TiO₂ anatase photocatalysts (without and with small amounts (~ 1%) of boron (B) that exhibit measurably different water-splitting activities. Note that the main aim of the current investigation is not to obtain top-performance samples but rather to understand the subtle role played by water at the solid interface and how this affects the photocatalytic water splitting rate. Thus, no metal was used as cocatalysts, and photocatalytic tests were performed in pure water at neutral pH rather than in an electrolyte solution.

By combining experimental physicochemical characterisations with state-of-the-art *ab initio* simulations, we demonstrate that doping with B atoms does not induce effects such as modification of the bandgap, crystal facets, morphology or formation of heterojunction commonly responsible for a promoted H₂ generation rate. Instead, the 5-fold increase in the photocatalytic H₂ production shown by the B-doped TiO₂ sample is due to the peculiar topology that the water H-bond network assumes at the liquid-solid interface upon doping. We find that B atoms on the TiO₂ surface change the local electric field, affecting the local H-bond network in the first water layers in contact with the semiconductor interface and, in this way, influence the outer-sphere electron transfer reactions. The alterations in the water structure were monitored by Fourier Transform Infrared (FTIR) measurements under various controlled relative humidity (RH) conditions and complemented by state-of-the-art spin-polarised Density Functional Theory molecular dynamics (DFT-MD) simulations.

Results

Water-splitting photo-behaviour

Figure 1a shows the cumulative H₂ production as a function of the irradiation time for both TiO₂ and (B)TiO₂ samples. There is a linear relationship between the formation of H₂ and the irradiation time, evidencing the absence of deactivation effects of photocatalysts. The H₂ and O₂ photoproduct ratio is stoichiometric (data related to the O₂ production are not reported for conciseness), indicating a water-splitting mechanism rather than water dissociation at surface oxygen vacancies. Furthermore, as displayed in Fig. 1b, the inclusion of B atoms in TiO₂ boosts the photocatalytic H₂ production rate, resulting in a remarkable enhancement of 4.6 times compared to that of pristine TiO₂, with rates of 20.1 μmol g⁻¹ h⁻¹ and 4.4 μmol g⁻¹ h⁻¹, respectively. Additional catalytic data are reported in the SI.

Fig. 1 | Water splitting photocatalysis. **a**) Hydrogen production (in μmol per gram of catalyst) as a function of the irradiation time over TiO₂ compared to (B)TiO₂. **b**) H₂ photoproduction rates.

Characterisation of the samples

Several physical-chemical characterisations have been performed to exclude that conventional interpretations for an enhanced water splitting rate are valid in our specific samples. Note that we do not indicate that B-doping does not alter the properties of TiO₂, but rather that the effects either are negligible or decrease the photocatalytic activity. Therefore, these effects cannot be used to interpret the enhanced photoactivity of B-doped TiO₂. The main results are summarised in Figure 2, while additional details are provided in the SI.

UV-vis diffuse reflectance spectroscopy (Fig. 2a and Supplementary Figs. 2 and 3a,b) does not reveal significant changes in the bandgap that could explain the augmented photocatalytic activity of (B)TiO₂. X-ray diffraction (XRD) analysis (Fig. 2b and Supplementary Fig. 4a) suggests that both powders crystallise in the anatase phase. Indeed, for both photocatalysts, the position and the relative intensities of the diffraction peaks in the XRD patterns (Fig. 2b and Supplementary Fig. 4a) are in good agreement with those of a conventional anatase TiO₂ structure (JCPDS card no. 21-1272). Thus, B-doping does not induce a change in the exposed crystalline facets, as confirmed by electron microscopy (see below). Similar to the XRD data, the Raman spectrum of both TiO₂ and (B)TiO₂ samples (Fig. 2c) displays five bands ascribed to the Raman active vibrational modes of anatase. As detailed in the SI, in the B-doped photocatalyst, the small shift in the position of diffraction peaks and Raman modes is consistent with incorporating the B atom in the TiO₂ crystal lattice.

Moreover, none of the techniques employed reveal the presence of boron oxide surface nanoparticles that would have affected the photocatalytic behaviour. As detailed in the SI, the slight position shift of the (101) XRD peak and the Eg(1) and B1g Raman modes indicate the incorporation

of B in the anatase TiO₂ structure.

Fig. 2 | Physical-chemical characterisation. **a)** Tauc plot of pure TiO₂ and (B)TiO₂. **b)** XRD pattern of pure TiO₂ and (B)TiO₂. **c)** Raman spectra of pure TiO₂ and (B)TiO₂. **d-f):** XPS spectra of O 1s **d)**: Ti 2p **e)**; and B 1s **f)** regions for both pure TiO₂ and (B)TiO₂ samples. **g-h):** DFT-MD modelling of titania surface. **g)** Zoom-in view of (101) TiO₂ surface: Ti_{cus} surface atoms coordinated to five oxygens in its pristine surface geometry. Ti and O atoms are pink and red, respectively. **h)** Zoom-in view of (101) (B)TiO₂ surface: B surface atoms coordinated to three oxygens. The two surface bond defects are highlighted in black dashed lines. Ti, O and B atoms are pink, red and cyan, respectively.

X-ray photoelectron spectroscopy (XPS) measurements provide further indications. The core-level XPS spectra of Ti 2p, O 1s and B 1s are shown in Fig. 2d-f. The results indicate the presence of B in interstitial sites, with about one-third of it on the surface of titania. This indication is confirmed by DFT-MD simulations of the (101) (B)TiO₂ water interface (see SI for computational details), where the doping with atoms of B at the surface creates local distortions of the pristine surface geometry of (101) TiO₂, leading to the formation of two bond defects at the surface (Fig. 2g,h). This is due to B³⁺, which is coordinatively saturated by three oxygen atoms in a trigonal geometry (and it is no longer surrounded by five oxygen atoms, as in the case of the replaced Ti_{cus}). Although we have experimentally observed that interstitial – rather than substitutional – B ions are mainly present in the bulk of TiO₂, about one-third are present at the surface, which agrees with our simulations. Surface

boron species introduce a residual charge, which can increase the number of surface OH groups.²⁴ Scanning Electron Microscopy (SEM) images with energy-dispersive X-ray (EDX) analysis (Supplementary Fig. 5) reveal a uniform distribution of particles with irregular shapes without any indications of a specific morphology or exposed crystal facets. Additionally, there is no apparent effect of B doping on these aspects. Moreover, doping with B does not significantly change the porosity characteristics (Supplementary Fig. 6 and Supplementary Table 3).

The comparative characterisation of TiO₂ and (B)TiO₂ indicates that doping with small amounts of B (1%) does not significantly modify the intrinsic properties of the semiconductor, such as the bandgap, crystal facets, morphology and porosity. About 30% of the B is present on the surface. The remaining B is present in the TiO₂ bulk, mainly as interstitial B. However, there are no indications that the interstitial B induces a downward shift of electronic band edges in our samples, which (for higher B loadings) could potentially justify an enhanced water-splitting activity.²⁵ Thus, the nearly five-fold enhancement of the water-splitting activity (Fig. 1b) must be ascribed to other factors.

It is worth pointing out again that our samples do not contain either metal nanoparticles or metal ions of Cu, Fe, noble metals and other metals (which may act as cocatalysts), even at trace level, as confirmed by chemical analysis. In other words, no cocatalysts are present, ensuring that the enhanced photocatalytic activity in the presence of B doping cannot be related to them.¹²

Characterisation data also exclude other possible causes for the enhanced performances of (B)TiO₂, such as the creation of heterojunctions or, as aforementioned, changes in the crystal facets or nanomorphology.²⁶ There is also no evidence of the formation of a built-in electric field²⁷ or a significant alteration in phase boundaries between different TiO₂ crystalline forms²⁸ in an amount that justifies the considerable increase in the activity.

Another alternative possibility is that defects on the TiO₂ surface could trap photogenerated electrons.²⁹ Photogenerated holes on TiO₂ are stabilised at bridging oxygen atoms,³⁰ while photogenerated electrons are located on the five-coordinated Ti atom on the TiO₂ surface.³¹ Thus, surface B atoms alter these processes and may change the surface stabilisation of these photogenerated charges. This evidence might explain the enhanced water-splitting activity of (B)TiO₂ with respect to TiO₂. However, the results in the following section prove this explanation is invalid for our samples.

Photoelectrochemical and photoluminescence results

To investigate the photogenerated charge separation, interfacial transfer properties and recombination rate, we made cyclic voltammetry (CV), chronoamperometry (CA), electrochemical impedance

spectroscopy (EIS) and steady-state photoluminescence (PL) measurements. Detailed results and related discussion are reported in the SI, while only the main findings are highlighted here.

Fig. 3 | Photoelectrochemical and photoluminescence characterisation. **a**) Cyclic voltammetry for TiO_2 and $(\text{B})\text{TiO}_2$ samples in 1 M KOH (solid and dashed lines for dark and light conditions, respectively). **b**) Chronoamperometric measurements for TiO_2 and $(\text{B})\text{TiO}_2$ samples (1.136 V vs RHE, 1 M KOH) using open UV-visible lamp spectrum (no light filter) and with light filter (AM1.5G, UVC, and UVB/C blocking filter). Data were normalised to the surface area of the photocatalysts. **c**) Photoluminescence spectra of TiO_2 and $(\text{B})\text{TiO}_2$ samples. **d**) Nyquist plot for TiO_2 (dots) and $(\text{B})\text{TiO}_2$ (triangles) samples measured in the dark (filled symbols) and light (open symbols) conditions, varying the applied potential (1.313, 1.713 and 2.133 V vs. RHE yellow, green and violet symbols, respectively). Symbols: experimental impedance data; dashed lines: fit made using the equivalent circuit model.

The CV and CA experiments, whose results are displayed in Fig. 3a,b, with and without irradiation by a solar illuminator, indicate that light illumination enhances water (photo)electrolysis at $(\text{B})\text{TiO}_2$ more effectively than at the TiO_2 surface in agreement with photocatalytic data (Fig. 1a,b). The effect might be due to either a more efficient stabilisation of holes at the surface, *e.g.* a more efficient charge separation³² and thus to a higher photocurrent generation, or (and) to the effect on the water structure at the interface, which enhances the coupled proton and hole transfer for water splitting.¹² The results of CA experiments (Fig. 3b) indicate that the photocurrent is independent of changes in the redox state of the semiconductor, as it may occur when activity is related, for example, to the presence of surface oxygen vacancies reacting with water.

When comparing the photocurrent results of TiO₂ and (B)TiO₂ under AM 1.5 G, UVC, and UVB/C filters, it becomes evident that the photocurrent density decreases when the UV components are removed. For instance, after cutting the light components below ≈ 400 nm, only about 20-25% of the open spectrum photocurrent remains. The decrease in the photocurrent density from the open spectrum case to AM 1.5 G filtered irradiation is slightly more pronounced in (B)TiO₂ than in TiO₂ (79% vs 74%). This indicates that 1% doping with B does not introduce a higher visible light activity than TiO₂. In both open spectrum and filtered illumination, TiO₂ exhibits the highest photocurrent density compared to (B)TiO₂. Therefore, B-doping does not enhance charge separation, which would have induced a larger photocurrent density.

PL experiments summarised in Fig. 3c demonstrate that i) B doping in our samples does not introduce intermediates states between the valence and the conduction bands and ii) the intensity of the PL emission in (B)TiO₂ is lower than that in TiO₂, indicating an elevated non-radiative recombination rate, i.e., the presence of significant loss pathways of charge carriers that do not contribute to the production of H₂, in agreement with CA results (Fig. 3b).

EIS experiments with or without illumination provide further insights. Under illumination, TiO₂ and (B)TiO₂ exhibit lower resistance to charge transfer, as displayed in Fig. 3d and Supplementary Fig. 7c,d. However, TiO₂ is characterised by a more significant interfacial charge transfer impedance than (B)TiO₂. Therefore, doping with B promotes electron transfers to water molecules. Nevertheless, the enhancement observed is not connected to a higher rate of charge generation on the surface, attributed to surface stabilisation or reduction of thermal degradation paths. Instead, the improved charge transfer is linked to promoting outer-shell transfer mechanisms.

These photoelectrochemical and photoluminescence indications, together with previous results, demonstrate that the promotion of the water splitting behaviour in (B)TiO₂ compared to TiO₂ has to be related to effects associated with the reorganisation of the water layer(s) in contact with the semiconductor rather than to other interpretations typically used in the literature to explain an enhanced photocatalytic activity by doping. Again, we emphasise that our samples were prepared *ad hoc* to avoid the concurrency of these alternative promotion mechanisms. Thus, we do not indicate that these mechanisms are invalid. Instead, in our samples, other relevant fundamental phenomena exist that are not accounted for by the existing literature.

Study of the water structure at the interface with the photocatalyst by FTIR

Essential insights on the local H-bonding environments of water molecules at and beyond the TiO₂ and (B)TiO₂ surfaces have been obtained by mid-infrared spectroscopic measurements at various

relative humidity (RH) levels by using a home-made cell (see SI and Supplementary Table 6 for the procedure details). This unique technique allows for directly inspecting the evolution of the structural water organisation (H-bond network) of the water molecules in the first layers in contact with undoped and B-doped TiO₂ surfaces rather than analysing the surface water chemisorbed species. The broad OH stretching band (2800-3600 cm⁻¹) has been primarily monitored because of its intense sensitivity to the H-bonded network. Indeed, it provides information on the various types of OH species in water.³³⁻³⁵ Besides, detailed features on water molecule interactions and the influence of microconfinement have recently been obtained by deconvolving this broad OH stretching band into five contributions (labelled as DAA, DDDA, DA, DDA and free OH).³⁶⁻³⁹ These components correspond to water molecules having different H-bond coordination numbers (ranging from 0 to 4) according to the number of H-bond donor (D) sites and H-bond acceptor (A) sites.⁴⁰ For example, a molecule in a DDAA configuration simultaneously donates and accepts two H-bonds. The DA H-bonding motifs exhibit an approximately linear structure, whereas other molecular patterns (DDAA, DDA and DAA) form three-dimensional H-bond networks.

Herein, to thoroughly depict the H-bond network of water on the titania surfaces, we have also monitored the FTIR signature of water in the less investigated – but instructive – HOH bending (1500-1800 cm⁻¹) zone.⁴¹⁻⁴³ Indeed, this vibrational mode provides complementary information to the stretching one on the single donor (D-type) and double donor (DD-type) water molecular arrangements. It shows how the presence of surface-water interactions⁴¹ influences them. From our FTIR experiments emerges a measurably different organisation of the H-bonds in the water layers at the surface of the undoped and B-doped titania samples, with the latter exhibiting a more significant number of DA motifs.

Fig. 4 shows the comparison of the FTIR spectrum of the undoped (blue lines) and B-doped (red lines) samples in the OH stretching (continuous lines) and HOH bending (dashed lines) regions at low (top panel) and high (bottom panel) RHs. Both bands are markedly broad and asymmetric in shape, especially in the B-doped TiO₂ case, suggesting the presence of heterogeneous arrangements of H-bonded water molecules close to the interface (first layers). Note that although the differences may appear minor, they are reproducible and show a clear trend with RH. The results are consistent with the literature data and correspond to modifications of bending and stretching modes. Differences are mitigated at high RH regimes where bulk-like behaviour is observed (Fig. 4, bottom panel).

It is relevant to note that what is analysed with this method is the structure (i.e., the H-bond network) of liquid water at the interface through intrinsic (inter)molecular correlations. This way, an inherent dynamic disorder is expected, leading to broad bands requiring deconvolution. As laid out

below, this operation has not been performed via a mere mathematical approach. Still, it has been executed while considering intrinsic physicochemical features supported by literature data. In addition, the parallelism between stretching and bending zones analyses further supports the interpretation.

Fig. 4 | FTIR spectra in the OH stretching (continuous lines with pink background) and HOH bending (dashed lines with light blue background) vibration frequency regions of water for TiO₂ (blue lines) and (B)TiO₂ (red lines). For better comparison, the IR intensity data are normalised to 1. Note that a higher H-O-H bending frequency (blue-shift) is typically associated with a lower O-H stretching mode frequency, indicating stronger H-bond networks.^{41,44,45}

In this work, the OH stretching band was deconvoluted into five Gaussian sub-bands with peak positions centred at ~3040, 3220, 3430, 3570 and 3636 cm⁻¹, corresponding to DAA, DDAA, DA, DDA and free water molecules populations, respectively.^{33,46} For both samples, the DDAA and DA bands are the most prominent at each RH value, contributing to more than 80% of the total integrated area of the OH stretching spectral vibration. They are, therefore, the only components reported in Figures 5a and 5b. Furthermore, the larger ratio of DA to DDAA populations for H₂O in the first water layers at contact with the (B)TiO₂ surface at all RHs (Figure 5e) implies a more prominent resilience to restore the tetrahedral coordination typical of liquid water. This finding indicates a slightly more hydrophobic character of the (B)TiO₂,³³ consistent with *ab initio* computations (see below).

The key finding is that the DA band dominates the spectrum in the (B)TiO₂ case, indicating an H-bond network with a prevalence of approximately linearly arranged H-bonded water molecules. Conversely, tetrahedrally coordinated water molecules are primarily present in the TiO₂ at all RHs. DDAA and DA bands are comparable in areas. As shown in Fig. 5e, the local water environment near the B-doped surface exhibits H-bonds motifs that are 20% to 90% richer in DA populations than in DDAA ones. In net contrast, the amount of DA and DDAA water arrangements equal each other at low RH in the undoped sample. In contrast, the tetrahedral water coordination is the most likely at larger RH values.

These findings are confirmed by the analysis of the HOH bending band (Fig. 5c,d), which has been deconvoluted into two Gaussian peaks centred at 1661 and 1612 cm⁻¹, corresponding to the bending frequencies for DDAA and DA water molecules, respectively.⁴²

Fig. 5 | Fourier Transform Infrared analysis. a-b: Gaussian deconvolution of the OH stretching band of the water environment at the proximity of a) TiO₂ and b) (B)TiO₂ samples at RH=33%. c-d: Gaussian deconvolution of the HOH bending band of the water environment at the proximity of c) TiO₂ and d) (B)TiO₂ samples at RH=33%. e) Mean H-bonding state of water in TiO₂ (blue bars) and (B)TiO₂ (red bars) samples.

In summary, our experiments indicate that the presence of small amounts of boron drastically influences the collective structure of the local water H-bond network and favours the formation of water molecules arranged into chain-like structures. In other words, the hydrophobic boron moiety hampers

the titania surface by DFT-MD simulations.

In conclusion, because of the introduction of B atoms, the titania surface becomes slightly hydrophobic, and the arrangement of interfacial water becomes considerably different. This is further corroborated by the data reported in Supplementary Table 4, showing each water molecule's average number of H-bonds as a function of the RH. Our results thus clearly indicate that the H-bond strength of the water environment at the interface with (B)TiO₂ is weaker than that in TiO₂. These findings might explain the larger water splitting rate observed in (B)TiO₂, which agrees with mechanisms recently proposed by Jiang et al.⁴⁸

DFT-based computational results

Quantum-level computations can further clarify the mechanistic interplay between the structure of water at the interface and the titania surface activity. Computational investigations have previously been employed to study titania materials, focusing on improving their photocatalytic properties.⁴⁹⁻⁵⁶ Most of these studies focus on the surface structure (without including the water layer), the formation of heterojunctions and heterostructures, and the surface reconstruction, adopting a static approach and an implicit solvent framework. However, the organisation of explicitly treated water (i.e., at the DFT level) at the interface (with a bulk density of 1 g/cm³), its dynamics at finite temperature, and their impact on the surface properties of a (B-doped) titania catalyst remain elusive. Previous investigations on the interaction of water with the titania surface were limited to the identification of chemisorbed species and, in some cases, the single or bi-layer organisation of water molecules on the surface of TiO₂.⁵⁷⁻⁵⁹ Only a few computational attempts provided insights about the dynamical H-bond environment at the TiO₂-water interface.⁶⁰⁻⁶³

What is not fully addressed yet, both theoretically and at an atomistic level, is how the modification of the surface properties (e.g., by doping), the reorganisation of the interfacial water environment as well as the surface ability of adsorbing/dissociating water molecules can affect the experimentally proven changes of the catalyst properties in the context of water splitting. Here, intending to fill this gap, we provide a detailed characterisation of not only the undoped and boron-doped anatase (101) surfaces of titania but also the dynamical finite-temperature behaviour of liquid water at the interface with the anatase (101) and anatase B-doped (101) TiO₂ by exploiting spin-polarised DFT-MD simulations. We overcome the most common static DFT picture and the implicit solvent scheme. DFT-based calculations were also performed on bulk anatase TiO₂.

The description of the computational approach and titania surface modelling is detailed in the SI. The (101)-TiO₂ surface was put in contact with 132 water molecules (bulk liquid water environment,

density $\sim 1.0 \text{ g/cm}^3$), leading to the solid-liquid water interface shown in Supplementary Fig. 15a. The same was done for the anatase (B)TiO₂/water interface (see Supplementary Fig. 15b). During our 25-ps-long DFT-MD simulations, we observed that exposing the (101)-anatase TiO₂ surface to liquid water stabilises the unsaturated Ti_{CUS} and O_{br} surface sites, the latter being able to absorb the entire/dissociated water molecules. The mechanisms by which water is adsorbed at the surface are shown in Fig. 7a,b. Water molecules can be either entirely surface-adsorbed (Fig. 7a) or dissociated (Fig. 7b) at the Ti_{CUS} surface sites.

Fig. 7 | Water interaction with the titania surface by DFT-MD simulations. a-b: Water adsorption **a)** and surface dissociation mechanisms **b)** at the (101)-anatase TiO₂ surface. The Ti and O atoms are pink and red, respectively. The water molecule is coloured in cyan.

Such surface wettability leads to a complete surface reconstruction that affects the structural and electronic properties of the (101)-anatase TiO₂, including the surface electric field and the surface catalytic features.⁶⁴⁻⁶⁶ Results of water-catalyst interactions by DFT-MD are summarised in Fig. 8b and discussed in the SI.

As aforementioned, water adsorption phenomena and H-bond interactions show a slightly hydrophobic character carried by the (101)-anatase (B)TiO₂ surface, where only 50% of the interfacial water molecules are H-bonded to the B-surface. Details are in Section 6 of the SI. Interestingly, the surface boron sites at the (101)-anatase (B)TiO₂ are not affected by water adsorption phenomena as well as by the interfacial H-bonds interactions, i.e. resulting in sites which are neither available for adsorbing/dissociating interfacial water nor for establishing H-bonds. When B atoms replace surface Ti atoms, they systematically relax as inner sites compared to the surface Ti atoms, i.e. B atoms move towards the solid sub-layer to fulfil their coordination (Fig. 2g,h). This fact is

further supported by evaluating the atomistic radial distribution functions (RDFs) (Fig. 8c) and, in particular, by comparing the RDF between titanium atoms Ti(s) at the surface and the water oxygen atoms O_w and that between boron atoms B at the surface and the water oxygen atoms O_w shown in Figure 8c (solid black and dashed blue curves, respectively). Ti(s) atoms are closer to water (exhibiting an average distance of ~ 2.1 Å) than (inner-site) B atoms, which are on average at ~ 3.9 Å from water oxygens.

Fig. 8 | Density Functional Theory molecular dynamics simulations. **a)** Magnification of the predominant surface-water H-bond pattern at the aqueous (101) TiO₂ interface. The H-bonded water molecule acts as an H-acceptor from the μ_1 -OH₂ and H-donor to the μ_2 -O site. Ti and O atoms are pink and red, respectively, while the water molecule is cyan. **b)** Water interaction with the TiO₂ surfaces by DFT-MD simulation. Equilibrium composition and speciation of the (101) TiO₂ (top) and (101) (B)TiO₂ (bottom) surfaces in contact with liquid water. The Ti, O, and H atoms are pink, red, and white, respectively. **c)** Calculated atomistic radial distribution functions (RDF). Ti(s)-O_w and B-O_w RDFs at the (undoped and doped) (101)-anatase/water interfaces are in black solid, red dashed and blue dashed lines, respectively. **d)** Isocontour of the local electric field determined as the difference of the electric fields between a system containing a Ti atom and a system containing a boron atom in the same position (the site coloured in yellow of the TiO₂ surface) for an isovalue equal to 0.10 V/Å.

The current experimental findings show that in our TiO₂ and (B)TiO₂ samples, the enhanced

water splitting of the latter is not due to a modification in the charge separation or a change in the water chemisorption sites given by the B presence. Instead, it is due to a local change in the structural organisation of the water molecules in contact with the solid surface. This fact is somehow related to the influence of doping on H-bonding and local electric fields. The presence of a Ti atom instead of a B one produces a local (within 3-4 Å) surface electric field intensity on the order of 0.10 V/Å oriented towards the water environment (i.e., isotropically outward the site), as shown in Fig. 8d. This local electric field, which is absent when B atoms replace the Ti ones, might be responsible for the more prominent hydrophilic character of neat TiO₂ with respect to its B-doped counterpart.

Electric fields of this strength can order the H-bond network of liquid water^{44,67,68} to a considerable extent, rationalising the larger structuring of the local water environment at the non-doped TiO₂ surface. This way, the surface properties are modified upon doping, which induces a relevant different interfacial water arrangement. These aspects are crucial in charge transfer phenomena at the interface, which depend on solvent reorganisations and local electric fields,⁶⁹⁻⁷¹ ultimately affecting the water splitting activity.

Discussion

Water splitting on semiconductors like titania TiO₂ and the impact of doping on their photocatalytic properties have been extensively studied in the literature.^{2-4,28,72-76} Various interpretations, such as crystalline facets, nano dimension, heterojunctions, heterophases, bandgap influence, and charge carrier dynamics, have been explored to comprehend the diverse photocatalytic properties of materials.^{5,26,32,75,77-80} However, one crucial aspect that remains unexplored is the specific nature of the water layer at the interface and its impact on the semiconductor photocatalytic activity.

The behaviour of water is intimately connected to its H-bond network,^{81,82} the latter being characterised by a dynamic equilibrium where H-bonds break and reform cooperatively across water clusters.⁸³ When water establishes H-bonds with the surface (influencing solvent reorganisation properties and the average nature of water clusters), the rate of outer-sphere electron transfer is affected in a way that only partially can be explained in terms of Marcus theory and derived models.⁸⁴ Doping alters the interaction of water with the surface, potentially influencing the water's nature at the interface and the outer-sphere electron transfer. Notwithstanding their manifest relevance, these aspects of water-splitting reactivity have not been investigated in the literature.

In this study, we designed two TiO₂ (anatase)-based photocatalysts, one doped with a low amount of boron (1%), which exhibited a five-fold enhancement in water-splitting activity compared to pure

TiO₂. We used various characterisation techniques, including XPS, XRD, Raman, UV-visible diffuse reflectance, and SEM-EDX, ruling out bandgap changes, heterojunctions, heterophases, and alterations in crystal facets, nanomorphology, or nanodimension as explanations for the enhanced photocatalytic properties.

Additional experiments, such as cyclic voltammetry (CV), chronoamperometry (CA), electrochemical impedance spectroscopy (EIS), and steady-state photoluminescence (PL), were conducted to exclude enhanced charge separation, charge stabilisation, and the creation of intermediate states as potential reasons for the enhanced properties of (B)TiO₂. State-of-the-art spin-polarised Density Functional Theory molecular dynamics (DFT-MD) simulations were also performed to examine the water chemisorption at the surface, confirming that B does not chemisorb water while reducing the amount of Ti_{CUS} that activates water molecules. Furthermore, B induces a slightly hydrophobic character on the titania surface, which is typically hydrophilic.

Our experiments and DFT-based numerical simulations demonstrate that the improved water-splitting activity observed in our B-doped system has to be exclusively linked to the water structure's local change at the B-doped interface and to the presence, in our experimental conditions, of a rate of H₂ evolution depending on outer-sphere electron transfer. The surface of the photocatalyst indirectly influences the rate because it shapes the local organisation of water molecules in the first layers at contact with the semiconductors. Thus, surface mechanisms of water splitting do not occur in our experimental conditions, unlike the predominant literature indications.^{76,85,86} The rate is determined from an outer shell electron transfer. While we cannot indicate whether this is the only relevant water-splitting mechanism, these results suggest that this outer shell mechanism, often neglected, plays a relevant role and can be used/tuned to design novel photocatalysts.

In summary, the intricate arrangement of water molecules at semiconductor interfaces profoundly influences photocatalytic systems, although other factors sometimes overshadow its significance. Our investigation unequivocally reveals that the structure of water, particularly the H-bonding network and local molecular configurations within the initial hydration layer, directly impacts the water splitting rate. The configuration of this water layer adjacent to the interface is intricately tied to its H-bonding with the semiconductor surface and subsequent water layers. This interaction is further modulated by surface doping. Recognising how the surface dictates specific H-bond motifs within the local water environment is pivotal for engineering more efficient photocatalysts tailored for water-splitting applications.

Materials and methods

Synthesis of TiO₂-based photocatalysts

The undoped and the 1wt% B-doped TiO₂ (TiO₂ and (B)TiO₂, respectively) were prepared via a sol-gel method by using tetra butyl titanate (TBT) and boric acid (H₃BO₃) as TiO₂ and B precursor, respectively. Specific details are given in the SI.

Photocatalytic water splitting test

Photocatalytic H₂ production tests over the undoped and B-doped TiO₂ samples have been done using an experimental setup consisting of a solar light source, a stirred photoreactor and a gas chromatograph. Further details are given in the SI.

Characterisation of the TiO₂-based photocatalysts

The samples were characterised by UV–vis Diffuse Reflectance Spectroscopy, X-ray diffraction (XRD), Raman spectroscopy, Scanning Electron Microscope (SEM) equipped with an energy dispersive X-ray spectrometer (EDX), X-ray photoelectron spectroscopy (XPS), N₂ physisorption to identify the surface area and porosity, and photoluminescence (PL). Details on the procedure and equipment are reported in the SI.

Photoelectrochemical characterisation

The electrochemical characterisation, including cyclic voltammetry (CV), chronoamperometry (CA) and electrochemical impedance spectroscopy (EIS) studies, were carried out by using an electrochemical cell working in a three-electrode setup. Details are reported in the SI.

Infrared Spectroscopy at controlled humidity conditions

Fourier-transform infrared (FT-IR) spectra in the mid-infrared region (MIR, spectral range 4000-380 cm⁻¹) were acquired in transmission (TR) mode using a Bruker Vertex 80V FT-IR spectrometer equipped with a home-made cell (Supplementary Figs. 12a-c). Details on the cell and procedure are given in the SI.

First-principles simulations

Spin-polarised Density Functional Theory molecular dynamics (DFT-MD) simulations of (101) anatase- TiO₂ and (B)TiO₂ at the interface with liquid water were performed within the Born-Oppenheimer framework employing the CP2K software package.^{87,88} Spin-polarised DFT calculations have also investigated the bulk crystalline structure of TiO₂-anatase. The Perdew-Burke-Ernzerhof (PBE) functional⁸⁹ was adopted with mixed Gaussian-Plane Waves basis sets and GTH pseudopotentials.⁹⁰ The PBE functional was chosen according to previous works, which show its

reliability for investigating titanium oxides and liquid water. The PBE functional was supplemented with the Hubbard U parameter,^{91,92} the on-site Coulomb interaction energy. An optimised U parameter value of 12 eV has been adopted to reproduce experimental structural bulk parameters such as lattice constant, bulk modulus and electronic properties such as the bandgap value of anatase TiO₂.

The DZVP-MOLOPT-SR basis set⁹³ and a 400 Ry plane wave basis set were used, and dispersion corrections were employed in Grimme's D2 framework^{94,95} after evaluating its accuracy and computational cost. Periodic boundary conditions (PBCs) were applied in all three spatial directions. DFT-MD simulations were performed in the NVT ensemble (~25 ps). Nosé-Hoover chain thermostat⁹⁶ kept a constant temperature of 300 K. A time step of 0.5 fs was adopted for the Velocity-Verlet algorithm.⁹⁷ No external biases (such as external potential) or pH changes have been applied. Further details are provided in the SI.

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Contributions

R.V., G.Ce., G. Ca. and G.D. conceived the research and developed experiments. R.V. conducted the majority of the experiments. F.T., C.A., and S.P. contributed to data collection and in paper revision. F.C., S.L. and G.Ca. executed, analysed and interpreted the first-principles simulations. R.V., F.C., G. Ce., G.Ca. and G.D. wrote the manuscript with input from all authors.

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Conflicts of Interest.

There are no conflicts of interest to declare.

Supplementary information

Additional results and experimental details are available in Supporting Information. Supplementary Methods, Supplementary Figures 1–15, Supplementary Tables 1–8, and Supplementary References.